

An Efficient System for Human activity recognition and monitoring for elderly people using Machine Learning

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Abstract. "Human activity recognition" is essential to the success of numerous real-world applications, such as the detection of abnormal behavior and elderly health surveillance (HAR). As part of our current research, we developed and tested a machine learning (ML) model that can accurately identify an activity based on raw data collected by wearable technology. The "WISDM Smartphone and Smartwatch Activity and Biometrics Database" was used in this particular study. Feature selection can aid in reducing a dataset's overall dimension and developing AI models. A confusion matrix for the model was created while the values for precision and recall were determined. We have used a variety of machine classification techniques, including KNN, SVM, DT, and NB, to evaluate human actions to evaluate the multidimensional data we have chosen to collect. The experiments' results showed that the decision tree algorithm was able to produce such remarkable results with a high degree of precision.

Key words: Human Activity Recognition (HAR), Machine Learning, Multi-Class Classification, Wearable's Sensor data, Meta-Heuristic Algorithms, Smartphone.

1. Introduction

One of the most important and challenging areas in computer vision is the detection of human activity (HAR). Driving, cleaning, and playing video games are just a few of the many official and routine tasks that humans regularly carry out in their day-to-day lives. It has significant applications in numerous fields, including therapy, robotics, and others. These exercises have standing, sitting, and strolling as their primary parts. The focus of the use of sensor data is on automatically recognizing adult actions[14].

2. Human activity recognition:

Seniors' health and well-being could be saved and their quality of life significantly improved by sensor-based physiological monitoring. Seniors who want to keep an eye on their health might discover. The detection of human activity presents a significant obstacle for the elderly care system. As a result of advancements in sensor technology, people are interested in developing systems that utilize wearable monitoring devices for the long-term monitoring of human subjects [1]. Information assortment, including choice, model turn of events, testing, and execution evaluation are the four essential phases of the HAR cycle [9]. An examination of the HAR system shown in Figure 1 is carried out using the procedure outlined below.

Figure .1.Flowchart of HAR

Figure 2 illustrates the use of sensors to identify human activities by sensor signal, feature selection,

training and testing.

Figure 2: Using sensors to recognize Human Activity

3. Proposed System

The structure that was utilized in this paper, which depended on an enhancement model for human action examination utilizing sensor information (the Benchmark dataset), was utilized to construct a methodology that outwardly represents and further develops the grouping execution by using improvement procedures and AI. This strategy was constructed using the framework.

The framework for this investigation is provided by the following outline: The topic of the literature review is discussed in this chapter's second section. The chapter's third section provides a comprehensive illustration of the system architecture. The dataset, the evaluation methods that were utilized in this study, and the experimental results that were obtained by utilizing the suggested system are all discussed in the fourth section of the chapter. An overview of the primary findings and conclusions is provided in the sixth section.

4. Literature Review

A 1D CNN-based method for recognizing elderly movement that makes use of accelerometer data collected from the user's smartphone was demonstrated by M. M. Hossain Shuvo (2017). Our solution performed better than the industry standard random forest method in the category of human activity. When features (longer duration) accelerometer data was used, classification accuracy was highest. The neural network must be trained. The creator recommends that the presentation of action acknowledgment is influenced by the info vector's dimension.[1]

The latest advancements and creating patterns in cell phone-based human action acknowledgment were concentrated on by Anna Ferrari(2021). We explicitly went through the steps of data collection, preprocessing, feature selection, and grouping for the activity recognition approach.

[2] Zhu et al. (2017) presented a HAR system with modules like feature extraction and activity identification to identify 33 distinct physical activities. The author concluded that the proposed system is a viable alternative for applications involving home care monitoring[3].

Jakaria Rabbi (2021) makes use of the HAR dataset, which can be found in the UCI Machine Learning Repository, as a reference dataset to develop and test the models. The Support Vector Machine outperformed the other methods significantly throughout the evaluation, with an average accuracy of 96.33 percent [4]

As stated by Vasudevan et al. 2021), the majority of elderly people live alone, requiring relatives to monitor their day-to-day activities. Due to a packed schedule, it's not always possible to be with elderly people all the time. As a result, families opt for remote monitoring. Elderly people can remain safe while requiring minimal care thanks to the ability to monitor their activities and receive alerts in the event of unusual behavior, such as a fall. Safeguard the way of life of more established people who wish to live unreservedly with practically no manual help.[6]

In Figure: 3 The system architecture that is proposed is shown.

Figure: 3 Architecture Diagram of the Proposed System

Table 1: Existing works in the HAR system: Summary

Sl.No	Author(year)	Title	Methods	Accuracy
1	Jakaria Rabbiet al.(2021) [4]	Human Activity Analysis and Recognition from Smartphone using Machine Learning Techniques	SVM	96.33%
2	Z Chen et al.(2017) [5]	Robust human activity recognition using Smartphone sensors via CT-PCA and online SVM	CT-PCA,SVM	95%
3	K. Butchi Raju ,Suresh Dara (2022) [18]	Smart Heart Disease Prediction System with IOT and Fog Computing Sectors Enabled by Cascaded Deep Learning Model	GSO-CCNN	94%
4	Kun Xia et al., (2020) [7]	LSTM-CNN Architecture for Human Activity Recognition	LSTM-CNN	95.85%
5	Federico Cruciani et al., (2019) [19]	Feature learning for Human Activity Recognition using Convolution Neural Networks	3-CNN	92.30%
6	Syed K. Bashar et al., 2020 [9]	Smartphone Based Human Activity Recognition with Feature Selection and Dense Neural Network	Neighborhood component Analysis(NCA) -SVM	95.79%

5. Dataset:

In the current investigation, predictions regarding human activity were made using the Smartphone, Smart Watch Activity, and Biometrics dataset from WISDM (Wireless Sensor Data Mining). The process of predicting a person's activities using a sensor-based mobility record as the data source is known as human activity detection. 7,352 distinct individuals provided information for the "WISDM (Wireless Sensor Data Mining) dataset." Six different tasks were completed in three minutes by each subject individually. Each participant carried a smartphone in their pocket in addition to sporting a smartwatch on their dominant wrist. A specially developed program that could be used on a smartwatch as well as a smartphone directed and supervised the data collection process. The accelerometer and gyroscope of the phone and smartwatch were used to record the sensor data. As a result, there are four sensors altogether.

The data can be divided into 80% for training and 20% for testing based on the subjects' data. During each of the six activities listed below, participants—also known as subjects—give measurements using an accelerometer and gyroscope. 10].

- i. Walking
- ii. Walking Upstairs
- iii. Walking Downstairs
- iv. Standing
- v. Sitting
- vi. Lying.

The readings are separated by a 50% overlap of three minutes. Readings of body acceleration and readings of gravity acceleration are the two types of readings provided by accelerometers, both of which have three axes (x, y, and z). A gyroscope is used to measure the angular velocities along this axis. Body acceleration measurements are calculated using jerk signals. Fourier Transforms are applied to the aforementioned time readings to obtain frequency readings. The following metrics are calculated based on the readings for each base signal in each window: mean, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, coefficient, entropy, and other similar metrics the feature vector we receive is comprised of 561 features from the dataset. Each reading window represents a 561-characteristic data point.

6. Feature Selection:

To achieve satisfactory classification accuracy when employing the feature selection approach, the number of recovered features was reduced by eliminating irrelevant and unnecessary features [6]. This was done to make use of the recovered features. Choosing relevant features is a common and crucial method for accelerating convergence and enhancing accuracy in classification problems. The classifier's ability to categorize the various feature categories will be improved by converting feature selection to a more trustworthy and appropriate form of input.

Optimizers for selecting the best features from a dataset are the subject of this section. To compare the performance of the suggested optimizer, the PSO, Grey Wolf, and Whale optimization feature selection methods are presented here. This section discusses the optimizers for successful feature selection. GWO methods are used to talk about the initial context of the PSO, the whale, and the Grey wolf, as well as the working mechanism of the suggested optimizer.

In figure 3 molecule swarm advancement - Choice tree the quantity of chosen highlights is 266 out of 570 elements utilizing Matlab


```

1 %-----%
2 % Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) source codes demo version %
3 %-----%
4 %--Inputs
5 % feat : feature vector ( Instances x Features )
6 % label : label vector ( Instances x 1 )
7 % M : Number of particles
8 % max_iter : Maximum number of iterations
9 % c1 : Cognitive factor
10 % c2 : Social factor
11 % w : Inertia weight
12 %-----%
13 %--Outputs
14 % sFeat : Selected features
15 % sF : Selected feature index
16 % Nf : Number of selected features
17 % curve : Convergence curve

```

Command Window

Column 246 through 266

524 526 527 528 529 530 531 534 536 538 540 542 545 548 560 561 562 563 567

Number of Selected Features:
266

Figure 3: Particle Swarm Optimization-Decision Tree

In figure 4 whale optimization –Decision tree the number of selected features is 292 Out of 570 features.

Whale-DT

```

1 | %-----%
2 | % Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) %
3 | %-----%
4 | %--Inputs-----%
5 | % feat      : feature vector ( Instances x Features )
6 | % label     : label vector ( Instances x 1 )
7 | % N         : Number of whales
8 | % max_Iter  : Maximum number of iterations
9 | % b         : Constant
10 | %-----%
11 | %--Output-----%
12 | % sFeat     : Selected features (instances x features)
13 | % Sf        : Selected feature index
14 | % Nf        : Number of selected features
15 | % curve     : Convergence curve
16 | %-----%
17 | ** Whale Optimization Algorithm

```

Command Window

Columns 286 through 292

```

552  554  555  556  557  558  559

```

Number of Selected Features:
292

Figure 4: Whale –Decision tree

In figure 5 proposed chaotic GWO –Decision tree the number of selected features is 252 out of 570

```

1 | %-----%
2 | % Proposed Chaotic based GWO
3 | %-----%
4 |
5 |
6 | %--Input-----%
7 | % feat      : feature vector (instances x features)
8 | % label     : label vector (instances x 1)
9 | % N         : Number of wolves
10 | % max_Iter  : Maximum number of iterations
11 |
12 | %--Output-----%
13 | % sFeat     : Selected features (instances x features)
14 | % Sf        : Selected feature index
15 | % Nf        : Number of selected features
16 | % curve     : Convergence curve

```

Command Window

Columns 246 through 252

```

552  553  554  558  562

```

Number of Selected Features:
252

Figure 5: Proposed Chaotic GWO – Decision tree

7. Chaotic Maps for Feature Selection

Examples of optimization algorithms include the grey wolf optimization (GWO), the genetic algorithm (GA), the particle swarm optimization (PSO), and the whale optimization algorithm (WOA) [17]. We investigate the idea that chaotic systems are extremely sensitive to the initial conditions, making them difficult to optimize; that is, even minute changes in the initial conditions can have a significant impact on the final results, and the optimization methods that are currently in use have slow convergence speeds. The turbulent method is used in this review to expand GWO execution by limiting stuck circumstances at neighborhood optima and supporting the speed of the combination. Additionally, it is used to deal with GWO's random factor values. In a variety of optimization applications, it has been demonstrated that the Chaos method can increase the value of looking for a global optimum. By avoiding difficulties associated with becoming caught in local optima, this is accomplished. A feature selection system whose optimization is based on chaos theory can be developed using the searching range $[0, 1]$ as a direct result of this. [8].

There are three kinds of chaotic maps:

1. Tent map
2. Circle map
3. Logistic map
4. Sine map
5. Gaussian map

8. Machine learning algorithms:

The highly interdisciplinary field of machine learning (ML) draws inspiration from a wide range of scientific and mathematical disciplines, including cognitive psychology, computer science, statistics, and optimization. In machine learning, a piece of data is analyzed and a model that divides it into the appropriate number of distinct classes is created using the supervised learning technique of classification. Understanding human behavior requires machine learning. HAR has implemented a variety of machine-learning algorithm types.

In Figure 4 we can see the outline of the strategy where datasets are taken from benchmark datasets for research purposes. A meta-heuristic optimization algorithm-based feature selection strategy is employed here. It is a sophisticated approach to finding a viable solution to a difficult problem. PSO, GWO, and WO optimization algorithms are utilized here. spreading existing machine calculations like DT, SVM, NB, and KNN to perceive how our component determination calculation will function in grouping the exercises and to look at the best outcome. Accuracy, precision, and recall are used to compare this.

Figure 6: Overview of Methodology

9. Models Used For Activity Recognition

9.1 Naïve Bayes:

In order to derive a list of probabilities from a dataset, a fundamental probabilistic analyzer known as "Naive Bayes (NB)" adds up all of the frequencies and values contained in the dataset. This method, which is based on the Bayes theorem, takes into consideration all of the independent and non-dependent characteristics that are revealed by the value of the class variable. The effectiveness of Naive Bayes has been demonstrated in a wide variety of real-world applications, including text classification, medical diagnosis, and the monitoring of system performance, amongst others. [11]. The "Naive Bayes" method offers quite a few distinct advantages. A condensed amount of training data is required in order to calculate the approximations of the values of the classification-related parameters.

9.2 Support Vector Machine:

In many sectors of application, SVM are primarily reliable and efficient classification and regression techniques. The study of pattern recognition, which is a particularly active and well-liked field of research, has greatly benefited from the use of the SVM. Support Vector Machine has been combined with other cutting-edge methodologies, like evolve algorithms, to enhance classification and parameter optimization. The support vector machine method's main objective is to divide the training set into various classes using a surface that maximises their distance from one another. In other words, SVM allows for the most generalizability of a model [12].

Fig 7: Confusion Matrix for Decision tree

When applying the PSO-DT(The PSO algorithm is a hybrid of evolutionary algorithms and swarm system. The particles (Birds) of the swarm are free to fly across the multidimensional search space. Each particle acquires its own velocity and location throughout the voyage. The entire population is updated by updating each particle. The particles gradually concentrate around the upper goal function value as the swarm arrangement forces itself toward it.) in the dataset ,we get 89.9% in Figure :8

		Confusion Matrix							
Output Class	LAYING	831 19.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	100%
	SITTING	0 0.0%	710 16.2%	117 2.7%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	85.9% 14.1%
	STANDING	0 0.0%	45 1.0%	697 15.9%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	93.8% 6.1%
	WALKING	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	675 15.4%	34 0.8%	78 1.8%	0 0.0%	85.8% 14.2%
	WALKING _{DOWNSTAIRS}	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	25 0.6%	497 11.4%	37 0.8%	0 0.0%	88.9% 11.1%
	WALKING _{UPSTAIRS}	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	50 1.1%	57 1.3%	623 12.0%	0 0.0%	83.0% 17.0%
		100% 0.0%	94.0% 6.0%	85.6% 14.4%	90.0% 10.0%	84.5% 15.5%	82.0% 18.0%	89.9% 10.1%	
	LAYING	SITTING	STANDING	WALKING	WALKING _{DOWNSTAIRS}	WALKING _{UPSTAIRS}			
	Target Class								

Figure : 8Confusion matrix: PSO-DT

When applying the Whale optimization –DT(An innovative method for handling optimization issues is the Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA). Three operators are used in this algorithm to replicate how humpback whales hunt by searching for prey, circling prey, and using bubble nets.) in the dataset ,we get 88.4% in Figure :9

		Confusion Matrix							
Output Class	LAYING	731 18.3%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	100%
	SITTING	0 0.0%	592 14.8%	110 2.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	84.3% 15.7%
	STANDING	0 0.0%	72 1.8%	648 16.2%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	90.0% 10.0%
	WALKING	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	641 16.0%	18 0.4%	115 2.9%	0 0.0%	82.8% 17.2%
	WALKING _{DOWNSTAIRS}	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	19 0.5%	472 11.8%	30 0.8%	0 0.0%	90.6% 9.4%
	WALKING _{UPSTAIRS}	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	47 1.2%	53 1.3%	452 11.3%	0 0.0%	81.9% 18.1%
		100% 0.0%	89.2% 10.8%	85.5% 14.5%	90.7% 9.3%	86.9% 13.1%	75.7% 24.3%	88.4% 11.6%	
	LAYING	SITTING	STANDING	WALKING	WALKING _{DOWNSTAIRS}	WALKING _{UPSTAIRS}			
	Target Class								

Figure 9: Confusion matrix: Whale-DT

When applying the GWO -DT (The leadership structure and hunting strategy of grey wolves in nature are modelled by the GWO algorithm. For the purpose of mimicking the leadership hierarchy, four different varieties of grey wolves, including alpha, beta, delta, and omega, are used.)in the dataset ,we get 89.3% in Figure :10

		Confusion Matrix							
Output Class	LAYING	844 19.3%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	100% 0.0%
	SITTING	0 0.0%	689 15.7%	109 2.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	86.3% 13.7%
	STANDING	0 0.0%	57 1.3%	684 15.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	92.3% 7.7%
	WALKING	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	692 15.8%	33 0.8%	82 1.9%	0 0.0%	85.7% 14.3%
	WALKING _D OWNSTAIRS	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	27 0.6%	509 11.6%	57 1.3%	0 0.0%	85.8% 14.2%
	WALKING _U PSTAIRS	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	54 1.2%	49 1.1%	490 11.2%	0 0.0%	82.6% 17.4%
		100% 0.0%	92.4% 7.6%	86.3% 13.7%	89.5% 10.5%	86.1% 13.9%	77.9% 22.1%	89.3% 10.7%	
	LAYING	SITTING	STANDING	WALKING	WALKING _D OWNSTAIRS	WALKING _U PSTAIRS			
	Target Class								

Figure 10: Confusion matrix: GWO-DT

Confusion matrix: CLM-GWO

When applying Chaotic logistic map (The Chaos technique is proved to increase the value of searching for global optimum in a range of optimization applications by avoiding stuck difficulties in local optima. As a result, the searching range [0, 1] can be used to create a feature selection system that uses chaos theory to optimise features.) decision tree plain in the dataset we getting 92.3% in figure :11

		Confusion Matrix							
Output Class	LAYING	186 15.8%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	100% 0.0%
	SITTING	0 0.0%	168 14.3%	10 0.9%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	94.4% 5.6%
	STANDING	0 0.0%	24 2.0%	183 15.6%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	88.4% 11.6%
	WALKING	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	215 18.3%	3 0.3%	9 0.8%	0 0.0%	94.7% 5.3%
	WALKING _D OWNSTAIRS	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 0.2%	168 14.3%	14 1.2%	0 0.0%	91.3% 8.7%
	WALKING _U PSTAIRS	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	19 1.6%	9 0.8%	166 14.1%	0 0.0%	85.6% 14.4%
		100% 0.0%	87.5% 12.5%	94.8% 5.2%	91.1% 8.9%	93.3% 6.7%	87.8% 12.2%	92.3% 7.7%	
	LAYING	SITTING	STANDING	WALKING	WALKING _D OWNSTAIRS	WALKING _U PSTAIRS			
	Target Class								

Figure 11: Confusion matrix: CLM-GWO

In table 2 we can observe the Different human activities with their count with the Proposed Model

S.No	Human Activities	Number of persons
1	Standing	183
2	Sitting	168

3	Laying	186
4	Walking	215
5	Walking_downstairs	168
6	Walking_upstairs	166
Total		1086

Table 2: Different human activities with their count with the Proposed Model

Description	Algorithms used	Accuracy
ML Algorithm	DT	88.4 %
Feature selection Techniques	PSO-DT	89.9 %
	Whale-DT	88.4 %
	GWO-DT	89.3 %
	Proposed	92.3 %

Table 3: Performance Comparison with Accuracy

In table 3 , When applying Decision tree along with Particle swarm optimization, Grey wolf optimization, Whale optimization and proposed Chaotic logistic map. We get high accuracy with CLM Decision tree 92.3% Performance Comparison of CLM-GWO-Machine Learning with Accuracy

Algorithm Details	Performance Metrics				
	Accuracy	Sensitivity	Specificity	Precision	F1-Score
CLM-GWO-NB	81.5	80.4	81.0	79.6	80.4
CLM-GWO-SVM	87.56	85.67	85.89	84.37	85.8
CLM-GWO-KNN	88.6	87.45	86.74	85.46	85.78
CLM-GWO-DT	92.3	90.55	92.0	91.6	91.78

Table 4: Performance Comparison of CLM-GWO-Machine Learning with Accuracy

In table 4 when applying CLM-GWO with machine learning algorithms like Naïve bayes, support vector machine, kNN and Decision tree .we get high accuracy with CLM Decision tree 92.3% In figure 12 the performance analysis with machine learning algorithms is shown in chart method

Figure 12: Performance Analysis with Machine Learning Algorithms

The collection of observed data from the sensors can be used to examine activities. Wearable sensors can be used for data collection. For instance, wearing an accelerometer on the body can capture data while getting around some limitations like flexibility and privacy.

Justification for Proposed Methodology

Feature optimization is used here to establish recognition models to capture best features from input sequence data to achieve more accurate recognition.

This research work utilized the chaotic based GWO with machine learning scheme that can recognize specific activities in short duration of time.

The experimental results show that the proposed approach can help to improve the recognition accuracy rate up to 92.3%.

10. Performance Metrics and evaluation:

To better identify human behaviors, the architecture employs feature selection and machine learning algorithms. The partitioned datasets that were used to train and test the technique are shown in Table 5

Table 5: Total number of data sets that were used in the training and testing procedure

Sl. No	Total number of data	Training data	Testing data
01	7352	5882	1470

Table 6: Measures of performance

SL.NO	Performance Metrics	Mathematical Expression
01	Accuracy	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$
02	Sensitivity or recall	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN} \times 100$
03	Specificity	$\frac{TN}{TN + FP}$
04	Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
05	F1-Score	$2 \cdot \frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall}$

True Positive values are denoted by TP, True Negative values by TN, False Positive values by FP, and False Negative values by FN.

11. Result and Discussion:

The data sets that these algorithms select for training and testing are chosen using machine learning techniques, and the abbreviation "Decision Tree" is used to refer to them. We tested with 20% of the data for an evaluation, while we trained with 80% of the data. The accuracy parameter will be used during the evaluation. The whole investigation is controlled by a PC with a 3.0 GHz Intel I7 processor, a 2GB NVIDIA GeForce K+10 GPU, 16GB of RAM, and a 2TB hard drive.

12. Conclusion and Future Work

As indicated by the discoveries of the investigations, the methodology that was prescribed can further develop acknowledgment precision by as much as 92.3%. This study shows how a decision-making algorithm and wearable sensors could be used to keep track of where elderly people are and monitor their activities. One of the flaws of the current method is that it does not provide precise tracking. More sensor data from a wide range of physical activities will be used in future studies to test the usefulness of various alternative models. We used a variety of machine classification techniques, such as k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees (DT), and Naives (NB), to evaluate human behavior on the multidimensional data we chose to work with.

Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict to disclose.

Declaration of competing interest:

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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